

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) AP_E_Bis_C_SQ_100K

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: AP_E_Bis_C_SQ_100K

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0040 A Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=6.9626(2) b=18.6664(6) c=8.6303(3)
 alpha=90 beta=109.095(4) gamma=90

Temperature: 100 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1059.94(6)	1059.94(6)
Space group	P 21	P 21
Hall group	P 2yb	P 2yb
Moiety formula	C26 H26 N4 O4	C26 H26 N4 O4
Sum formula	C26 H26 N4 O4	C26 H26 N4 O4
Mr	458.51	458.51
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.437	1.437
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.099	0.099
F000	484.0	484.0
F000'	484.21	
h, k, lmax	9, 25, 11	9, 25, 11
Nref	5844 [3006]	5253
Tmin, Tmax	0.972, 0.986	0.977, 1.000
Tmin'	0.972	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.977 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.75/0.90 Theta(max)= 29.380

R(reflections)= 0.0422(4470)

wR2(reflections)=
0.0899(5253)

S = 1.002

Npar= 307

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level G**

PLAT032_ALERT_4_G	Std. Uncertainty on Flack Parameter Value High .	0.300	Report
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C1 (Sohncke SpGr)		R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C1A (Sohncke SpGr)		R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C5 (Sohncke SpGr)		R Verify
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G	Model has Chirality at C5A (Sohncke SpGr)		R Verify
PLAT899_ALERT_4_G	SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL	2019/3	Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min). 0 2 0,		1 Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600		181 Note
PLAT916_ALERT_2_G	Hooft y and Flack x Parameter Values Differ by .	0.50	Check
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G	The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value	2.521	Note
	Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 3.57 or SHELX Weight	8.97	
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		7 Info

- 0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
0 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
11 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected
- 0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
2 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
1 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
7 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check
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It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

